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#Let'sBeatCoronaTogether

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Contextualising Maulana Azad and His Educational Philosophy for Our Times

Mushtaq Ahmed I Patel* and Wadudul Haque Siddiqui

Born in Mecca and raised in Calcutta, Maulana Azad was home schooled in religious instruction. He never attended formal education and remained mostly self-taught throughout his life. These facts notwithstanding, he lived a prodigious life throughout. Before he was twelve, he began his literary career with *Nairang e Alam* (a poetic journal) and *Al Misbah* (a weekly magazine which he edited). At the same time, the little boy was also seen busy in establishing a library, a reading room and a debating society on his own. He soon began contributing literary articles to *Makhzan* (a literary magazine) and, by the age of fifteen, he was found teaching a class of students, most of whom were twice his age. It was, therefore, not much surprising that the boy completed the traditional course of learning at sixteen, nine years ahead of his contemporaries.

There is an interesting anecdote worth mentioning here. According to SG Haider, one of his biographers, "Urdu speaking people once invited a learned scholar, whose writings they had learnt with admiration, to address a national-level conference in 1904. But when a lean and thin, unbearded fair complexioned Maulana Azad barely sixteen, alighted from the first compartment, thousands of his admirers at the Lahore railway station could not believe their eyes" (Pant, 2010). Haider further observes, "...when this boy gave a memorable extempore speech, for more than two and a half hours, the President Maulana Hali, who was in his late sixties and already a known name, hugged him lovingly, saying, "...of course my dear boy, I now believe my senses, but I am not yet able to overcome my utter surprise" (Pant, 2010).

Maulana Azad was a man of many qualities. He was a linguist, mastering Persian and Arabic besides Urdu, Hindi and English; an internationalist, who travelled extensively in the Arab and Muslim worlds and gained a deep understanding of the main currents in those societies; a scholar who read widely and kept a profound, even encyclopaedic, knowledge of political and social issues (Hindu, 2007); an educationist, one of the founding members of the Jamia Millia Islamia University in Delhi; a journalist and writer, who started, edited and wrote India's first nationalist newspapers in Urdu; and a man of action, who led the Khilafat movement and the Dharasana agitation,

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and who remains the youngest-ever President of the Indian National Congress, having been first elected to that position in 1923 at the age of barely 35 (Hindu, 2007).

The scholars have examined the personal qualities of Maulana Azad from the eyes of his contemporary leaders, who thought that he was an extraordinary person, admired by many. Pandit Nehru considered his mind like a razor, which cut through a fog of ideas, who contributed his ideas on religion, state and civil society in India. That is why; Nehru referred to Maulana Azad as 'Mir-E-Karwan'. In the words of Mahatma Gandhi, 'I consider Maulana a person of the caliber of Plato, Aristotle and Pythagoras' (Rizvi, 2018).

Maulana Azad was ardently opposed to the idea of partition. However, despite all his efforts, he could not stop the creation of Pakistan. Later, in a well-known speech in Delhi, he predicted, "These two countries (India and Pakistan) will now focus on the military and society will not develop" (Ahmed, 2011). It is quite unfortunate to see that the for boding of Maulana Azad was indeed true, for we still have to achieve a lot to be called a mature society.

After Partition, Maulana Azad understood his historic role as the country's most important Muslim leader; in his person, he symbolised the new democracy's guarantee that his co-religionists could remain in their homeland in security and dignity (Tharoor, 2007). In the wake of Partition, he travelled extensively in the regions rent by communal carnage, directing the organisation of relief work and setting up refugee camps, making powerful speeches to large audiences to promote peace in the newly drawn border areas and encouraging his fellow Muslims throughout India to remain loyal to their homeland, without fear for their safety and well-being (Tharoor, 2007).

Ideas in Education: His Perspective, Our Context

As independent India's first Education Minister, Maulana Azad emphasised upon several issues, including his attempts towards secularising and constitutionalising Indian education; facilitating common access to education, including highlighting its social aspects; promotion of culture, learning in vernacular languages and championing the cause of women's education. He took relevant steps in realising

these ideals and could achieve substantially in the process. While addressing the meeting of the Central Advisory Board of Education, on 15 March 1952, as the Minister of Education, he put forth the five-fold programme to expand education in the country. These included:

- a. Universal compulsory basic education for all children of school age;
- b. Social education for adult illiterates;
- c. Measures for improvement in the quality of and expansion of facilities for secondary and higher education;
- d. Technical and scientific education on a scale adequate for the nation's needs; and,
- e. Measures for the enrichment of the cultural life of the community by encouraging arts and providing facilities for recreation and other amenities.

History tells us that facts and figures are witness to the powerful legacy he left behind as the first Education Minister of independent India. A few points about his legacy are discussed in this article.

Idea of Identity in a Democracy

Fard Qayam Rabt-e-Millat se hai, Tanha Kuchh Nahin
raun-e-Dariya Kuchh NahinMauj Hai dariya mein aur Ba

(ALLAMA IQBAL)ع

*The individual is firm by nation's coherence,
otherwise he is nothing;
Much like the wave which is only in the ocean,
outside it is nothing*

Muhammad Iqbal, who actively supported the creation of Pakistan through his poetry, held the view that individual identity springs from the idea of a community. In other words, it is the feeling of belongingness to a nation that empowers an individual's identity. Maulana Azad held a similar yet differing perspective on identity. For him, both religion and culture formed a basis of identification in a democratic state. He, however, also held the view that in a constitutional democracy, secularism remains the biggest leveller. He favoured religious instruction and learning in the vernacular medium, and at the same time, he also required education to be regulated and standardised by the state. In his opinion, what mattered most was public participation in a democracy, which could only be achieved through social education in

the ideals of the constitution. While emphasising upon his Muslim identity, he observes: "I am proud of being Indian. I am part of the indivisible unity that is Indian nationality. I am indispensable to this noble edifice, and without me, this splendid structure is incomplete. I am an essential element, which has gone to build India. I can never surrender this claim" (Pant, 2020).

Reacting to the creation of Pakistan, Maulana in his celebrated work, *India Wins Freedom*, observes: "As a Muslim, I, for one, am not prepared for a moment to give up my right to treat the whole of India as my domain and share in the shaping of its political and economic life. To me it seems a sure sign of cowardice to give up what is my patrimony and content myself with a mere fragment of it" (Azad, 1959).

In our globalising world, there is nothing more important than issues in individual, group and national identities. A great extent of our social and professional spaces is filled with individual claims of identity—our Facebook posts, our YouTube subscriptions and personalised channels, self-promotion videos and our professional networking on Linked. In everything speaks of identity claims. Politics of our times is also amassed with claims of group identity—religion, ethnicity, culture all seem to be at the service of public claims in social identity. Similarly, debates around freedom of movement, refugee crisis, and citizenship all seem to be based on claims of national identities. What better example of this claim could be better than Brexit, i.e., the exit of Great Britain from the European Union?

Professor Kenneth Robinson (2010), the famous British Educator in his talk, takes the identity claims to the next level. He notes that the current patterns of education throughout the world, especially school education, are increasingly aligned with the patterns of religious, social and cultural identities. Where on the one hand, parents are eager to expose their children to global curricula and learning methods, they are also concerned about the ideas in identity which these children imbibe. They do not want their children to be swept away in the wave of globalisation, losing their self-identities. They instead want them to retain their cultural and religious identities while being active participants in the global economy.

These developments remind us of Maulana Azad's approach, where he suggested a child should

be instructed, in the early stages of his education, through the medium of the mother tongue. He also emphasised that all educationists agree that any departure from this principle is bound to be harmful to the child and, therefore, to the interests of the society (Kumar, 1992). It was only this approach that led to vernacular instruction in primary education in India.

Access to Knowledge and Learning Outcomes

Access to knowledge remains one of the biggest hurdles of our times. The opportunities in education and training, limited as they are, also seem meek and hardly appreciable. How, then, do we perceive the outcomes of our learning? More importantly, how do we structure our educational pedagogy in these changing times? These are some of the biggest issues of our times. We are witnessing the deteriorating state of our institutions of learning, where students are not eager to study, and the teachers lack the ability of engagement. Moreover, in this era of liberal institutions, our educational domains have also become value-neutral. We do not seem to be in the mood to impart knowledge using correct teaching methodologies and curricula. It remains our assumption that every teacher is pre-equipped with the relevant teaching and training techniques.

Maulana Azad was a prominent proponent of free and compulsory education at primary levels. He observed: "A good school is a national asset of the highest value at any place or at any time. Schools are the laboratories which produce the future citizens of a State. The quality of the State therefore depends upon the quality of such laboratories. In the context of modern India, the importance of good schools is even greater. On the one hand, we have vast illiteracy and on the other, almost unbounded opportunities," (Kumar, 1992).

While also voicing his opinion for women education, in 1949, he observed: "No programme of national education can be appropriate if it does not give full consideration to the education and advancement of one-half of the society, that is, the women" (Kashyap, 1989). In his estimation, the student of today had to be looked at as a potential leader of tomorrow and, therefore, if students are not properly trained, they cannot supply the correct leadership which the nation will require (Khaleefa, 2014).

Simon Sinek, famous motivational speaker and author, in one of his interviews observes that our education systems seem ill-equipped to teach present-day students. While on the one hand, our educational systems seem grossly out-dated in terms of resource availability; we also tend to greatly underestimate the psyche of the millennial generation (i.e. people born around the 1990s). It is because of these reasons that teaching in classrooms has become complicated and we continue to falter in achieving the intended outcomes of our learning processes. In his view, we need to change our educational patterns to facilitate a proper learning atmosphere for our students (Crossman, 2016).

Bill Gates (2016), in his Ted Talk on *Teachers Need Real Feedback*, highlights the relevance of feedback in efficient teaching. He observes that feedback from the students has a positive impact on learning processes and, in the longer run, produces intended outcomes. Similarly, Daphne Koller (2012), in her Ted Talk on *What We're Learning from Online Education*, highlights the positive outcomes of online learning. In her estimation, skill centric learning imparted in open groups facilitating student interaction, is known to have produced the desired learning outcomes.

Maulana Azad viewed gaining education as a transformative process. He not only kept primary education, but also secondary and tertiary levels of education dear to his heart. In his estimation, academic institutions have not only academic functions, they have social responsibilities as well. When seen from this perspective, Maulana Azad's ideas seem to be as relevant today as they were in the past. While we need to promote education in all its forms (both online and offline) and establish institutions of learning, it is pertinent that we also find out that the processes bear the intended fruits. Maulana Azad gave life to *Anjuman-Tarraqui-e-Urdu-e-Hind* (Society for Progress of Urdu in India) and increased the grants of Jamia Millia Islamia and Aligarh Muslim University during the periods of their financial crisis. Moreover, he also gave priority to the Archaeological Survey of India in its efforts to repair and maintain protected monuments (Khaleefa, 2014).

Promoting Education Towards Social Ends

Addressing the Conference on All India Education, Maulana Azad, in 1948, emphasised that

education is the birth right of every individual and that basic education was necessary for an individual to discharge his duties as a citizen (Pant, 2010). Adult education and participation were, therefore, found central to the educational philosophy of Maulana Azad. He observed, "If there is any one feature which distinguishes modern India, it is the growth of the spirit of democracy which seeks to give equality of opportunity to all its citizens. All past barriers based on birth, privilege, caste or wealth are breaking down. As a secular democratic state, we pledge to the widening of opportunities and equality of chances for all..." (Kirpal, et. al, 1990).

It is for these reasons that Maulana Azad stressed on the importance of the speedy progress of adult education and observed that without an educated electorate, democracy cannot perform the functions expected of it. It was also for these reasons that he wanted the scope of adult education to also include provision for social education.

Are these ideas relevant in our context? Of course, yes! Otherwise, how could we promote the ideals of democratic participation and mutual respect among the citizens of the country? What else could have abolished untouchability, enshrined in Article 17 of the Constitution? Looking prospectively, if not adult education and training, what else can strengthen brotherhood (also sisterhood), highlighted in the Preamble to the Indian Constitution under the ideals of *fraternity*?

Patel (2016), in one of his articles, "*Taleem aisi Ho (keM ukammala khbarS amajh mefA(aye)*" Education should be such that they can understand the whole newspaper, describes what type of education is required today. It is briefed that the newspapers contain varied information on contemporary issues, historical documents, documentaries, sports, business, science, technology, politics, economics, health etc., of the nation, across the globe and beyond. Academic, political issues are discussed and debated to promote national goals and integrity of the nation. Hence, Maulana who himself was running various newspapers and magazines was highly educated in this sense and strived for education of all.

Institutionalisation of Learning

Maulana Azad believed in the institutionalisation of education. He established institutions of learning,

while also streamlining the learning processes. As the Minister of Education of free India, he felt that, alongside basic school education, imparting technical education of the highest standards was also of paramount urgency. One of the first decisions that he took over as Minister was that the government must ensure establishment of institutions of the standard of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in India. At the Opening Session of the Indian Institute of Technology at Kharagpur on 18 August, 1951, he observed that the Institute must provide instruction of the highest standard, under the supervision of recognised authorities in their respective fields and that only men [persons] of the highest quality should be in charge of the different departments. In the field of technical education, he strengthened the All India Council for Technical Education, which soon established a chain of IIT's at Bombay, Madras, Kanpur and Delhi. He also established the School of Planning and Architecture during his tenure in 1955.

The Moral Legacy of Maulana Azad

āteñ haiñZ ahīñK ahīñ aurK irqa-bandī haiF
āteñ haiñB ahīY anapne kīP amāne meñZ yāK

(ALLAMA IQBAL)ع

*(We are divided across varying identities;
Is this what is required to constitute a progressive
society?)*

Two ideas require special attention here, first, Maulana Azad's caricature of India and its society; and second, his understanding of the role of students in nation building. Some of his quotes which bring home the points are presented here.

He argued that the Indian men and women were required to contribute effectively in nation-building: *"We want in India of future, men and women of vision, courage and honesty of purpose, who will be able to play their part worthily in every field of national activity"* (Chatterjee, 2010).

Let us contextualise these words against the Convocation Speech he delivered before the students of Aligarh Muslim University in 1949. Emphasising on the role of students in nation building, he noted: *"You are the citizens of free India—a State which is determined to develop its political and social life on secular and democratic lines. The essence of a secular and democratic State is freedom of opportunity for*

the individual without regard to race, religion, caste or community. As members of such a State, you have therefore the right, provided you have the necessary qualities of character and attainment—to expect all doors to open to you, whether in the field of politics, trade, industry service or the professions. There is no gain saying the fact that in the past, many of the alumni of this institution looked to nothing but employment under the Government. Freedom must bring in a widening of the mind and an enlargement of your ambitions. You must therefore look forward in a free India to the utilization of your talents in the manner best suited to the needs of the Nation. I have no doubt in my mind that if you can imbibe this spirit of progressive nationalism, which is the motto of our secular democratic State, there will be no position in any field of life that will be beyond your reach. I would, therefore, urge upon you to develop and strengthen your character and acquire knowledge that will fit you to play your rightful part for the future progress and prosperity of the country" (Chatterjee, 2010).

Learning in Our Times

Some ideas which we believe and follow, are highly relevant for effective learning in our institutions. The *Six Attributions in Academic Engagement*, as authors call them, should guide better instruction and learning across all levels of education. Authors confess, with their experiences in higher learning, they have taken a liberty in framing these rules. The intention is merely to guide teachers towards achieving their instructional objectives.

Subject Expertise

A good teacher is someone who has domain knowledge and expertise in the subject. They reflect this both in the manner in which they deal with technical issues in the subjects and the reference they make while addressing those issues. The teacher must be able to understand the emerging issues and the underlying currents under them.

Student Engagement

Student engagement is the pre-requisites for an excellent teacher. Reading a text and attending a class are two separate things. The presence of excellent teachers makes all the difference. They cannot deliver the knowledge of the subject to the students but are also capable of holding the attention of the class. Teaching, therefore, is both a mix of

substance and delivery—understanding the literature, their contexts, their analysis and interpretations. With the millennial, delivery is more important to classrooms now.

Teaching Environment

The teaching environment in a classroom needs to be congenial for meaningful engagements. Gone are the days we considered when learning as a one-way traffic—from teacher to student. The knowledge process is now understood as creating a mutual learning environment for both the students and the teachers. Therefore, the classroom must not only be comfortable for the teacher but also for the students. It should be capable of holding and carrying forward the expressive environments built between the tutor and the tutee. The greatest contributor to such an environment is, without doubt, a forthcoming teacher. Learned Islamic Scholar Malik ibn Anas once proclaimed, "Learn good manners before seeking knowledge". We sincerely believe that one cannot be a forthcoming teacher without seeking a proper learning environment from the students.

Relationship Building

A teacher must have the ability to build relationships with the students. Learning environment is one domain where human relations are fundamental—students cannot learn from their teachers if they do not enjoy a comfortable relationship. A teacher must, therefore, not only be capable of holding the interests of the students, she/he must also inculcate the emotional quotient in the students. This comes in two ways—first, understanding why a particular field of knowledge is relevant for individuals and the society; second, contextualising the study both in present as well as in the future. They can also achieve this by employing the problem-solving approach while teaching the subject.

Moral Standing

No matter what the critics say, a teacher has to take moral responsibility towards meaningful learning. While a teacher enters the class to deliver lectures, students on the other side do not merely take away the knowledge of the subject, rather they also unconsciously gain the personal traits of the teacher. We all are products of our environments; we cannot therefore deny the fact that an excellent teacher also

carves talented students; an outstanding teacher leaves a legacy of outstanding student-achievers.

Learned Islamic Scholar Muhammad ibn Idris al-Shafi'i once returned to his home and knocked at the door of his house. His mother asked him what he came back with? (meaning, what all did he learn). He replied he had come with knowledge (*ilm*) and etiquettes (*adab*). His mother sent him back saying that he perhaps learned nothing. Shafi'i went to his teacher Malik ibn Anas, who told him, tell your mother that you returned with etiquette (*adab*) and knowledge (*ilm*). With only this reply, he could find an entry in his home! The lesson from the story is this—the etiquette of seeking knowledge always precedes acquiring knowledge.

Honesty and Appreciation

Lastly, teaching is a profession of learning; learning stops where the buck stops. It is, therefore, necessary that a teacher must appreciate ideas from the students, accept her/his lack of knowledge, acknowledge the contribution of the students and be expressive of her/his limitations. Students always like teachers who are honest in their approach and work hard in overcoming her/his limitations.

It seems quite germane here to quote a beautiful couplet from Iqbal:

īrāñ seV-isht-eK qbāl' apñI' ā-umīdN ahīñ haiN
aaqīS arqhez haiZ ahutB iTTIM am ho to yeN arāZ
(ALLAMA IQBAL)

(Iqbal, I am not hopeless in my hardship; a little shower of rain and the earth will be green again)

Conclusion

Maulana Azad's contributions as Freedom Fighter and Patriot; Statesman and Parliamentarian; Leader and as Education Minister are immense in building the nation. He was a man of integrity, wisdom, and vision. As an educationist, he was successful in putting the lock straight for the achievement of the intended goals. His vision and commitment helped him in steering through rough roads and overcoming the hard conditions and circumstances of laying down the base of education at primary, secondary, tertiary, technical and research levels.

Maulana Azad's contribution in strengthening democratic and secular values through education,

providing opportunities for education to the people, particularly the masses and working toward social engineering, are monumental as well as of great importance. He left a legacy and a lesson to learn from the present and future generation of citizens of this country.

Note: ¹The Urdu couplets transcribed in English script were provided by the Authors.

²The article is published to commemorate National Education Day.

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